

STABILITY AND ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL OF ALUMINIUM OXIDE HYDROSOL

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In the region of slow coagulation, the apparent electrokinetic potential ζ_a of an Al_2O_3 sol has been measured both by the electro-osmotic and electrophoretic methods in the presence of equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes containing counter ions of different valency. A plot of $1/\zeta_a$ against $1/S$ (where S represents the bulk specific conductivity of the supernatant liquid in equilibrium with the coagulum) yields a straight line in agreement with the equation

$$1/\zeta_a = 1/\zeta + m \frac{1}{S}$$

discussed in previous papers. From the intercept of the straight line on the $1/\zeta_a$ axis, the value of true ζ has been calculated. The results lead to the conclusion that a given rate of coagulation of the Al_2O_3 sol by different electrolytes is characterised by a definite value of the true ζ -potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

The role of electrokinetic potential in determining the stability of colloids has engaged the attention of many investigators. Hardy (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1900, **A**, 66, 110) first suggested that a colloid coagulated when it was isoelectric with the dispersion medium. Powis (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, **89**, 188) on the basis of his own experiments and those of Ellis (*ibid.*, 1912, **80**, 597) put forward the theory of critical potential for coagulation of colloids. The experimental results on arsenious sulphide and silver iodide sols (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **109**, 734; *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, **78**, 32) do not seem to support this theory. In all these experiments, however, the ζ -potential has been calculated from the Smoluchowski equation, which according to various workers does not give the correct value of this potential owing to neglect of surface conductance and other factors.

According to Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1954, **31**, 273, 394; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 955) the electro-osmotic equation for a diaphragm, taking correction for surface conductance into account, is of the form

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{2\tau\chi}{\zeta} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where ζ represents the true electrokinetic potential and ζ_a , the potential calculated on the basis of the Smoluchowski equation, τ , radius of the capillary equivalent to the average pore of the diaphragm, χ , the specific surface conductance of the particles and S , the bulk specific conductance of the liquid; α is a correction factor for diaphragm introduced by Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1955, **32**, 69, 402; *Naturwiss.*, 1955, **42**, 121).

For large values of κa , the electrophoretic equation of Henry (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948, **44**, 1021) and Booth (*ibid.*, 1948, **44**, 955) can be put in the form (Ghosh *et al.*, *Nature*, 1955, **176**, 1080)

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_a} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{\chi}{\zeta \cdot a} \cdot \frac{1}{S} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where 'a' represents the radius of the particles ; κ is the characteristic term of the Debye-Hückel equation, the other terms having the same significance as before.

By utilising equations (1) and (2), given above, attempts have been made to measure the electrokinetic potential of aluminium oxide sol in the presence of comparable concentrations of electrolytes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sol was prepared by adding a concentrated solution of ammonia dropwise with continuous stirring to a solution of aluminium nitrate, maintained at 70-80°. Addition of ammonia was stopped when the precipitate formed dissolved very slowly. Two litres of the sol, thus prepared, were dialysed for about three months and then stored in a stoppered Jena bottle where it was allowed to age for a month.

The aluminium oxide content of the sol was 4.1 g./litre and its ρ_{H} and specific conductance were 5.08 and 3.500×10^{-3} mhos respectively.

Determination of Equicoagulating Concentrations.—The electrolyte solution (2 c.c.) was mixed with the sol (2 c.c.), left as such for 18 hours and then the mixture was centrifuged for 2 minutes at a definite speed. The supernatant liquid from the top was pipetted into a clean dry test tube and examined for turbidity or transparency. The concentration of electrolyte, which on addition to the colloid gave just a clear supernatant solution by the above treatment, was taken as its equicoagulating concentration.

Separation of the Coagula from the Supernatant Liquid.—The sol (40 c.c.), mixed with the electrolyte solution (40 c.c.) of equicoagulating concentration, was allowed to stand for 18 hours. The coagula were then separated from the supernatant liquid by centrifuging and were used for electro-osmotic experiments. The clear supernatant liquid was used for electro-osmotic as well as for electrophoretic experiments.

Electro-osmotic Experiments

The coagula, separated from the colloid-electrolyte mixture (40 c.c. of each), were transferred to a U-shaped tube which was then centrifuged at a given speed.

The volume of diaphragm in all cases was maintained constant as far as practicable by regulating the time of centrifuging. This ensured more or less the same degree of packing and the same average size of the pores when equicoagulating concentrations of different electrolytes were used so that α and τ in equation (1) for endosmosis should remain constant. The two side-tubes of the U-tube were connected *via* pressure tubings and two three-way stop-cocks to a glass tube having a narrow uniform bore and four rectangular bends. The U-tube containing the diaphragm was filled with the supernatant solution, separated from the coagula, and clamped in a thermostat bath (35°). With the help of the two three-way stop-cocks, the bent tube was filled with water and an air-bubble of length of about 0.4 cm was drawn into it. The electric field was applied through the platinum black electrodes, immersed to a definite depth inside the two limbs of the U-tube. The liquid flowing through the diaphragm caused the air-bubble to move. From the rate of movement of the air-bubble, the current flowing through the U-tube, the specific conductance of the supernatant solution, the cross-section of the bent tube and other relevant data, ζ_s was calculated. The data are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

$$\text{Temp.} = 35^\circ. \quad \zeta = 28.6 \text{ mv.} \quad m = \frac{2 \lambda}{\zeta \cdot \tau} = 4.06 \times 10^{-6}.$$

Electrolytes.	Equicoagulating conc.	Sp. cond. of supernatant soln. (5×10^6).	ζ_a	
			Obs.	Calc. from eq. (1).
NaCl	$6.198 \times 10^{-2} N$	771.40 mhos	28.0 mv.	28.1 mv.
Na_2SO_4	9.324×10^{-4}	13.42	14.2	15.3
$\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	4.209×10^{-4}	4.943	8.5	8.5
NaCl	2.066×10^{-4}			
&	&	7.771	11.5	11.4
$\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	3.988×10^{-4}			

Electrophoretic Experiments

A modified form of Burton's U-tube apparatus was used for electrophoretic measurements. Each limb of the U-tube carried a stop-cock of wide bore, the cross-sectional area of which was the same as that of the limbs. The thistle funnel, the tube connecting it through a stop-cock to the bottom of the U-tube, and the entire lower part of the U-tube up to the upper level of the stop-cocks in the limbs were filled with the colloid-electrolyte mixture. The upper limbs were nearly filled with the clear supernatant liquid having the same conductance as that of the intermicellar fluid of the colloid-electrolyte mixture. The colloid-electrolyte mixture was prepared in the following way. The sol (20 c.c.) was mixed with 20 c.c. of the electrolyte of equicoagulating concentration and the mixture was allowed to stand for 30 minutes for attaining equilibrium and was then used in Burton's tube.

After the apparatus was fitted up in the way described above, small specially designed calomel electrodes were dipped into the supernatant liquid at the top of the U-tube. The level of the liquid in the two limbs was adjusted and the stop-cocks were opened. The stop-cock connecting the thistle funnel was also carefully opened so as to allow the colloid-electrolyte mixture to rise slowly in the limbs. When the colloid-liquid boundary stood at a level of about 2.5 cm above the stop-cocks, the flow from the thistle funnel was stopped by closing the stop-cock. The current was now switched on. It was regulated by an adjustable resistance and measured by a sensitive microammeter. The cross-sectional area 'A' of the limbs of the U-tube, where the boundary moved, was also determined. The potential gradient was found from the expression $i/A \cdot K$, in which 'i' represents the current and K, the average of the specific conductances of the supernatant liquid and the colloid-electrolyte mixture.

After the upward movement of the boundary was observed, the colloid was found to coagulate slightly. So in order to measure the rate of downward movement, another similar experiment was carried out with fresh boundary, made of fresh colloid-electrolyte mixture and the supernatant solution. The current in this case was, however, allowed to pass in the reverse direction. Mean values of ζ_a for upward and downward movements are presented in Table II. The electrolytes used in electrophoresis always contained a small quantity of NaCl to ensure reversibility of the calomel electrodes.

TABLE II

$$\text{Temp.} = 28^\circ. \quad \zeta = 31.0. \quad m = \frac{\chi}{\zeta \cdot a} = 2.198 \times 10^{-6}.$$

Electrolytes.	Equicoagulating conc.	Sp. cond. of supernatant solution ($S \times 10^5$).	Sp. cond. of colloid-electrolyte ($S' \times 10^5$)	ζ_a .	
				Obs.	Calc from eq. (2).
NaCl	$6.198 \times 10^{-2} N$	699.7 mhos	696.0 mhos	30.5 mv.	30.7 mv.
NaCl & Na_2SO_4	2.066×10^{-4} & 8.880×10^{-4}	14.49	14.20	19.6	21.0
NaCl & $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	2.066×10^{-4} & 3.988×10^{-4}	7.013	6.836	16.3	15.7
NaCl & $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	1.033×10^{-4} & 3.998×10^{-4}	5.625	5.374	13.6	13.6

In Fig. 1, the length of the vertical lines in the electro-osmotic curve I indicates the maximum range of variation of $1/\zeta_a$ in five different experiments.

DISCUSSION

It will be noticed from endosmotic data recorded in Table I and from curve I in Fig. 1, that a straight line is obtained when the reciprocals of ζ_a are plotted against reciprocals of the corresponding conductances of the supernatant solutions. Hence, it follows from equation (1) that ζ and m , and consequently χ (since m contains χ), for the sol remain constant at the equicoagulating concentrations of the different electrolytes used. The value of true ζ , found from the intercept on $1/\zeta_a$ axis, is 28.6 mv.

FIG. 1

An examination of the electrophoretic data in Table II (Fig. 1, curve II) also indicates that there exists a linear relationship between $1/\zeta_a$ and $1/S$ as is to be expected

from equation (2). This confirms the conclusion which we have already drawn from the electro-osmotic data. The value of true ζ , found from the intercept on $1/\zeta_0$ axis in the electrophoretic measurements, is 31 mV. The average of the values of ζ , found by the electro-osmotic and electrophoretic measurements, is 29.8 and this may be taken as the true ζ , potential of the Al_2O_3 sol in the presence of the equicoagulating concentrations of the electrolytes used by us. It may therefore be concluded that a given rate of coagulation of aluminium oxide sol is characterised by a definite value of the true ζ -potential, independent of the valency of the counter ions used.

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